

STANDARDIZATION OF LABOR AS ONE OF THE METHODS OF LABOR PROTECTION

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Abstract. *Labor standardization is one of the ways of protecting the labor of employees by developing recommendations aimed at studying, improving and improving working conditions. The main task of labor standardization is to determine the optimal time and rules for performing work based on the psychophysiological characteristics of a person.*

Keywords: *standardization of labor, weight (strain).*

In modern times, the penetration of techniques and technologies into every aspect of human activity has radically changed the views on the field of labor protection and caused a number of problems in the system. The main means of solving these complex problems is labor standardization. By further improving the current labor standardization, all resources are used wisely, which is one of the important tasks of employers. The introduction of improved time standards on a scientific basis leads to the optimization of the number of employees, as well as to the improvement of work organization, to increase the production capacity by calculating the actual volume of work. Estimated time standards are aimed at clearly defining the functions of employees, which allows for rational and economical use of working time. The method of labor standardization is a set of methods for studying and analyzing labor processes, determining the price of working time, determining and taking into account the factors that create the standard, designing a rational organization of labor, and developing standards [1, 120]. It should be noted that the study of working time norms is becoming one of the important scientific directions. Conducting research in this regard is of great scientific and practical importance, because based on the obtained information, the following tasks related to the organization of labor and its regulation are solved: number of employees; time standards; downloads.

The new version of the Labor Code stipulates that the normal length of working time for an employee cannot exceed forty hours per week in a five-day or six-day work week. The length of working time for medical workers, educators and other categories of employees whose work is associated with a high level of mental, mental and nervous stress, that is, of a special nature, is a maximum of thirty-six hours per week. is defined as The list of such employees and the exact duration of their working hours is determined by the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan, but it is determined in such a way that it does not exceed the duration of working hours specified in this article. Duration of daily work (shift).

Duration of daily work (shift):

- a) for employees whose normal length of working time is determined for themselves:
 - in a six-day working week - seven hours;
 - in a five-day working week - eight hours;

b) for employees under the age of eighteen - from the duration specified in Article 416 of this Code;

c) for employees with disabilities - from the duration specified in the second part of Article 427 of this Code;

g) for employees employed in jobs with unfavorable working conditions - it cannot exceed the duration specified in Article 478 of this Code.

Social and labor issues by the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan for creative employees of cultural and entertainment organizations, television, radio broadcasting organizations and other mass media, professional athletes, as well as other persons participating in the creation and (or) performance (demonstration) of works According to the agreement with the tripartite commission of the republic, the duration of the daily work (shift) can be determined in accordance with the legislation, internal documents, collective agreement or labor contract.

In case of introduction of cumulative accounting of working hours in the organization, the provisions provided for in Article 199 of this Code shall be applied. [2, 106-107].

Labor standardization is a very complex process based on consideration of all factors affecting labor efficiency and productivity. In labor standardization, the method of standardization is selected based on the specific requirements set by the customer. The main tasks of normalization of labor are as follows:

introduction of reasonable organizational, technological and labor processes, creation of necessary conditions for improvement of labor organization;

to ensure the normal level of stress (intensity) of work in the performance of work and the provision of public services;

regulation of the permanent and variable part of employees' wages, improvement of the wage system

Steps of calculation of labor standards

Labor standard is the basis of organizational provision of employees' activities. Labor standardization is the main tool that incorporates the parameters of evaluating various options for organizational provision of employee activity. Due to the fact that organizational changes have a certain impact on working time, labor standardization makes it possible to evaluate these changes and choose the most optimal option.

The method of labor regulation

It is important to study and observe the working time during the service process in the organization and regulation of work. The main purpose of tracking time consumption by dividing each process into operations is:

determining the working time spent on performing operations and operation elements, finding, studying, analyzing methods and techniques improved by employees and putting them into practice;

determining the best methods, methods, procedures of effective work or service delivery, as well as the reasons for inefficient use of working time;

determining the most optimal consistency in the execution of some parts (elements) of operations;

obtaining the necessary and sufficient information for the internal distribution of labor in production and service enterprises, the organization and planning of labor in conveyor production and servicing of multiple devices and workplaces;

to determine the reasons for the loss of working time in production and service provision and the possibilities of increasing labor efficiency;

determining the reasons for compliance or non-compliance with labor standards; effective use of working time and identification of opportunities to increase labor efficiency. According to the results of my experience obtained through timing, below are the inter-sectoral time norms of professions with different ratios of mental and physical labor:

Standards of sample states for the number of employees of children's health centers									
(Employees of the Chatkal Children's Health Center)									
#	Occupations (name of position)	position	Duration of work <i>(number of timings, minutes-seconds)</i>					Average execution time min	Stability K= max/min
			The composition of the work to be performed						
			1	2	3	4	5		
1.	Head of the camp	Check the area	50	52	48	49	51	50	1.1
		Kitchen preparation control	15	13	16	14	17	15	1.3
		Control of children's awakening	10	8	12	11	9	10	1.5
		Control of squads and number of children in sports fields	15	17	14	16	13	15	1.3
		Control of the condition of the medical room (employees and children who complained about their health)	15	13	14	16	17	15	1.3
		Pool readiness control	15	17	14	16	13	15	1.3
		Morning breakfast control	80	76	78	82	84	80	1.1
		To study the activity of circles	15	13	14	16	17	15	1.3
		Working with additional offers and appeals	30	32	34	26	28	30	1.3

		Assigning and monitoring the implementation of additional proposals and solutions for appeals	70	67	68	73	72	70	1.1
		Supervision of daytime activities	45	47	46	44	43	45	1.1
		Pool readiness control	15	17	14	16	13	15	1.3
		Working with parents	60	55	57	65	63	60	1.2
		Lunch control	110	106	112	108	114	110	1.1
		Working with documents (from organizations and organizational issues)	120	115	125	126	114	120	1.1
		2-breakfast control	15	13	16	14	17	15	1.3
		Dinner control	80	83	80	80	77	80	1.1
		Evening events	120	115	125	120	120	120	1.1
		Nighttime sleep control	40	38	41	42	39	40	1.1
		Work with educators (Division of duties)	15	17	14	16	13	15	1.3
		Working with Leaders (Division of Duties)	15	13	16	14	17	15	1.3
		Various domestic issues (Working with Security Service)	15	17	14	16	13	15	1.3
	Educator		20	19	25	18	24	21.2	1.39
		Cleanliness check	38	46	40	39	52	43	1.33

2.		Distribution to classes	8	9	11	8	9	9	1.38
		Swimming training	60	60	75	70	80	69	1.33
		Supervise children's bathing	67	65	70	75	73	70	1.15
		Lunch control	42	44	45	55	48	46.8	1.25
		Organizing their vacations	134	130	140	150	143	139.4	1.15
		Organization and control of hygiene	97	90	100	110	103	100	1.22
		Organization of various events	77	70	80	90	83	80	1.29
		Dinner control	35	37	40	45	43	40	1.22
		Organization of cultural events	90	85	87	93	95	90	1.12
		Control of evening washing	35	37	43	40	45	40	1.22
		Night sleep control	15	20	17	25	23	20	1.47
		Night control	190	195	197	210	209	200.2	1.08
		Shift transfer	17	19	20	15	18	17.8	1.33
	Doctor	Working with magazines	15	13	16	14	17	15	1.31

3.	Group Control Cleanliness and Health)	55	52	55	54	56	54.4	1.08
	Placing portable quartz lamps in rooms	60	62	58	59	61	60	1.07
	Check the cleanliness of the kitchen	40	44	43	41	40	41.6	1.10
	Food inspection, sampling and storage	50	57	55	43	45	50	1.33
	Checking employees	25	24	27	26	27	25.8	1.13
	Admission of children (with health complaints)	20	24	22	23	20	21.8	1.20
	control	10	9	9	12	11	10.2	1.33
	Get an analysis	10	10	10	9	11	10	1.22
	Medical treatment	10	9	11	10	10	10	1.22
	Blood pressure check	3	2.4	2.5	2.8	3.1	2.76	1.29
	Pool control	25	29	33	27	31	29	1.32
	Check the groups	50	60	62	65	68	61	1.36
	Physical education training	30	30	30	30	30	30	1.00
	Sports events	60	60	60	60	60	60	1.00

		Hygienic and preventive measures	21	22	20	19	20	20.4	1.16
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Conclusion. Thus, labor regulation is the most important method of labor protection, it serves to preserve the health of workers, increase production efficiency and create safe working conditions. The introduction of labor standards requires the development of individual standards for each type of work with a detailed analysis and ensuring their implementation under control. Labor protection through the regulation of labor allows to achieve the following main goals:

Prevention of excessive weight (strain) that is appropriate for each employee during the performance of his duties - working within the specified limits can lead to occupational diseases, various diseases and physical injuries. , allows to reduce mental and psychological excess tension. Standardization of the production process makes it possible to determine the optimal ratio between time and the volume of work performed, which, in turn, increases the efficiency of production and increases the service life of equipment.

Determining labor productivity by monitoring the fulfillment of standards set by employees - monitoring the labor productivity of employees and ensuring timely identification and prevention of problems that may arise.

Prevention of industrial accidents and injuries related to the work process - determination and optimization of working hours, taking into account working conditions, prevents the occurrence of dangerous situations that lead to injuries or accidents.

Improving working conditions and standard of living of workers - normalization of labor includes the creation of favorable conditions for the performance of work, rest, rest breaks, as well as the establishment of appropriate wages. The specificity of a specific branch and type of work is of particular importance in labor regulation. When defining norms and rules, it must be carried out on the basis of special studies and data analysis to take into account the relevant factors affecting the quality and safety of work.

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